

Effect of phosphorus fertilization on “priming” of native phosphorus by rice in acid soils of Assam

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Four typical rice-growing soils of Assam received three levels of phosphorus under continuous submergence and continuous moist conditions in the greenhouse. The uptake of soil phosphorus

was determined by radiochemical analysis. The quantity of “primed native phosphorus” was calculated:

$$\text{“Primed native phosphorus” (uptake in mg/pot)} = \frac{[(\text{Total-P uptake} - {}^{32}\text{P tagged fertilizer-P uptake}) - \text{Soil-P uptake (control plot)}]}{\text{uptake (control plot)}}$$

Fertilization with phosphorus as superphosphate increased the dry matter yield of rice and phosphorus (see table) uptake. The contribution of superphosphate not only was direct but was due to its “priming effect” on the uptake of native soil phosphorus — probably by

helping in the early vigorous growth of roots to exploit more soil. Under continuous submergence, the quantity of primed soil phosphorus of different levels of phosphorus fertilization was significant compared to the fertilizer phosphorus uptake by the crop at those levels. The results suggest that fertilizer phosphate application under continuous submergence is a beneficial practice that allows use of the immobilized soil phosphorus by the rice crop. ■

Quantity of “primed native soil phosphorus” at various rates of phosphate fertilization (SSP)^a under different moisture regimes during 1978. India.

Location	Uptake of “primed native soil phosphorus” (mg/pot) by the rice crop								
	Continuous submergence (M1)			Continuous moist (M2)			Av of M1 + M2		
	P1	P2	Mean of P1 + P2	P1	P2	Mean of P1 + P2	P1	P2	Mean of P1 + P2
Titabar	23.76	33.15	28.45	8.80	7.40	8.10	16.28	20.28	18.28
Dergaon	19.76	48.31	34.03	5.32	5.07	5.19	12.54	26.69	19.61
Golaghat	31.07	24.17	27.62	1.36	1.20	1.28	16.22	12.69	14.45
Tengakhat	31.06	33.58	32.32	10.60	7.65	9.13	20.83	20.61	20.72
Mean for all soils	26.41	34.80	30.61	6.52	5.33	5.93	16.47	20.07	—

^aSSP = single superphosphate. Phosphorus levels were P1 (60 kg P₂O₅/ha) and P2 (120 kg P₂O₅/ha). The rice was Pusa 2-21.

Rice-based cropping systems

Effect of rainfall pattern on the shift in farmers’ rice cropping patterns in Bangladesh

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A severe and prolonged drought in 1979 affected the cropping patterns and crop yields in many areas of Bangladesh. The rainfall pattern and the cropping patterns that farmers followed were monitored at a rainfed, double-rice crop (aus-T. aman) cropping systems research site at Bhogra, Joydebpur, Dacca, and compared with those of 1978.

The 1978 rainfall pattern was normal and unimodal (see figure). The fields received enough rainfall by April to

Rainfall pattern and farmers’ rice cropping patterns in 1978 and 1979 at a rainfed double-rice-crop area, Bhogra, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh. Areas of other cropping patterns are not shown in figure (1978 = 8%, 1979 = 14%). HYV = high yielding varieties.

